

A CUDA enhanced 3DLS-DEM+FEM scheme for grain swelling induced by transient heat conduction

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Abstract

We introduce a generalized 3DLS-DEM+FEM scheme that allows, for the first time, the computational simulation of heat conduction and thermo-elastic expansion of arbitrarily shaped particles. In this multi-physics scheme, the particle kinetics and kinematics are computed using the 3D Level Set - Discrete Element Method (3DLS-DEM), where each individual particle shape is accurately represented by means of a Three-Dimensional Level Set (3DLS) mathematical function. Meanwhile, the heat conduction problem is numerically solved by the Finite Element Method (FEM), where a tetrahedron-based mesh is obtained for each grain directly from its corresponding LS function. Moreover, particle volumetric change due to the effect of temperature variation is modeled by modifying the LS functions through the application of a thermo-elastic constitutive law for small strains. Once the aforementioned methods have been combined, a benchmark numerical test is performed in order to fine-tune the model parameters. A second test is performed to simulate and analyze the effects of temperature variation on thermal volumetric expansion, stress, and hysteresis. Finally, for this study and due to the high computational cost that is implied in solving the heat conduction problem for each particle, we leverage Intel's Math Kernel Library (MKL) and NVIDIA's Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA).

Keywords: 3DLS-DEM, FEM, Level Set function, heat conduction, small thermo-elastic deformations, grain swelling, Intel's MKL, CUDA.

1 Introduction

Granular materials play an important role in numerous human activities such as mining, produce handling, pharmaceutical industry, construction and waste management [1]. Since soil is one of the most abundant resources on the planet, the study of granular materials allows for a better understanding of the behavior of soil in natural phenomena such as landslides, erosion, liquefaction, and pavement cracks induced by thermal stress. Therefore, this subject matter can have important implications in many human pursuits.

Thus, being able to predict the behavior of this type of matter, makes it possible to solve real-world engineering problems, leading to more efficient and economical processes, or possibly averting future catastrophic scenarios. In spite of these promising applications, granular assemblies usually exhibit non-linear behavior, mainly related to grain shape and grain-to-grain interactions (e.g., mechanical, electrostatic, capillary, thermic). These microscopic interactions play an enormous role on the macroscopic properties of granular assemblies [2, 3].

Although there is considerable literature related to phenomenological models for predicting macroscopic behavior of granular assemblies [4, 5], most of them fail to capture and incorporate the effects of microscopic interactions. Further on, experimental [6, 7] and computational studies demonstrated that grain-to-grain interactions have important implications when it comes to macroscopic properties of granular assemblies, particularly, on their strength and dilation. For this purpose, the Discrete Element Method (DEM), introduced by [8], emerged as an attempt to shed light onto the microscopic behavior of granular materials. However, this method failed to properly incorporate grain shape and its effects on the bulk behavior. Hence, a method that accurately captures the real grain shape while maintaining an affordable computational cost is 3DLS-DEM [9]. This method captures the shape of the grain by using Level Set (LS) functions, thus providing an efficient contact algorithm. Furthermore, other schemes have been developed that use 3DLS-DEM as a basis, while also taking into account micro-scale phenomena such as electrostatic cohesion [10] and grain breakage [11, 12].

In the present study, the aforementioned 3DLS-DEM scheme is enhanced in order to simulate the thermo-elastic phenomenon in a soil sample. For the purpose of integrating the thermo-elastic phenomenon, it is necessary to first solve for the temperature distribution within each grain's do-

main. Thermal diffusion is governed by the transient heat conduction equation, which describes how heat diffuses through a solid over time [13]. Analytical solutions of this equation are limited to symmetric geometries and boundary conditions. Hence, this type of solution is not feasible for complex geometries, non-linear material properties, or irregular boundary conditions. Consequently, solutions for these cases can be approximated only by means of numerical methods. In dealing with arbitrarily shaped objects, the Finite Element Method (FEM) is decidedly the best option for solving the spatial derivatives of transient heat conduction equation. However, the FEM is not optimal for approximating time derivatives [14]. Given that the stated problem is also time-dependent, these derivatives are approximated with the Forward Euler finite difference scheme.

Thermal-induced stress occurs when a material is subjected to a variation in its temperature, leading to expansion-contraction processes. Materials expand when heated mainly because, as atomic vibrations increase, inter-atomic distances do so as well, ultimately causing the material to swell. Inversely, when a material is cooled, the atomic vibrations decrease, leading the material to contract. In isotropic materials, the contraction or expansion produced by temperature variations occurs uniformly in all directions and is characterized by the coefficient of thermal expansion [15]. This work demonstrates that it is possible to simulate a grain's thermal expansion-contraction mechanism by manipulating its corresponding level set function.

The present work is divided into nine sections, as follows: in section 2, we focus on defining the LS function and the DEM scheme, 3DLS-DEM, which allows for accurately representing not only arbitrarily shaped particles, but also their grain-to-grain interactions. Then, in section 3, we describe the process by which the FEM is used to solve the transient heat conduction equation as applied to the arbitrary shaped particles. Three-dimensional linear tetrahedral elements are used to discretize the LS functions from section 2. Section 4, presents the combined 3DLS-DEM + FEM scheme, enabling the simulation of multi-body (grain-to-grain) heat conduction. Within section 5, the thermal grain swelling method is integrated into the previously described scheme. This allows for the simulation of the expansion-contraction in the grains as induced by thermal initial and boundary conditions (assuming that the grain mass is homogeneous and isotropic). In section 6, a flow chart describes how the aforementioned methods, i.e., 3DLS-DEM + FEM + thermal Grain Swelling Function are coupled together along with the initial conditions and required data for the simulation.

Next, in section 7, a numerical benchmark test is carried out. This test uses the digitalized level set representations of 29 grains from a real sample of martian regolith simulant. Out of the test results, the sample’s mechanical and thermo-plastic behavior is analyzed as the container wall’s temperature is linearly increased until reaching a plateau at 353K. Moreover, section 8 presents the optimization of the implemented scheme by leveraging High Performance Computing (HPC) libraries, such as Intel’s Math Kernel Library (MKL) and NVIDIA’s CUDA. This ultimately results in significant gains in terms of computational resources when applied to a larger sample of 100 martian regolith simulant grains. This test is based on the study of the response yielded by a drained specimen of Opalinus clay [16]. In the computational test, the sample is subjected to thermal cycles ranging from 298.15K to 353.15K, and starts at a mean hydrostatic stress of $0.483[\frac{kgf}{cm^2}]$ (confinement pressure). Here, the effect of temperature variation on the elastic expansion-contraction of each grain and how it translates into the elasto-plastic behavior of the packing as a whole is studied in detail. This, while reducing the computational cost by 85.90%.

Finally, in section 9, further improvements for this newly introduced method are proposed. Among these: the implementation of the Crank-Nicholson method to replace the Euler finite difference scheme, the use of a denser mesh to improve accuracy for the solution of the FEM equations, and the inclusion of more GPUs as well as the further optimization of the 3DLS-DEM C++ code to further reduce simulation processing times.

2 Three-Dimensional Level Set-Discrete Element Method (3DLS-DEM)

2.1 The Level Set function

In this section, a brief description of the LS function is given. According to [17], a LS function is a signed distance function divided into three separate regions, one negative, Ω^- , that represents the space inside of the grain, another positive, Ω^+ , that represents the space that lies outside of the grain, and a frontier region between these first two, called the interface, $\partial\Omega$, which just lies on the surface of the grain, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A color heatmap of a slice of a LS function, where the negative region, Ω^- , is represented by negative signed values (bluer contour lines) and the positive region, Ω^+ , is represented by positive signed values (redder contour lines). These two regions are delimited by the interface, $\partial\Omega$ (black contour line).

According to the previous concept and by first having defined the smallest uniform distributed grid with spacing L that can contain the LS function, for any given point, \mathbf{x} , of this LS grid, the minimum distance between this point and the interface, $\partial\Omega$, is then calculated, as in eq.1:

$$d(x) = \min(|x - x_i|) \quad \forall x_i \in \partial\Omega \quad (1)$$

Given these minimum distances, the LS function, ϕ , can then be defined at every point, \mathbf{x} , of the LS grid by the piecewise function shown in eq. (2):

$$\phi(x) = \begin{cases} +d(x) & \forall x \in \Omega^+ \\ d(x) = 0 & \forall x \in \partial\Omega \\ -d(x) & \forall x \in \Omega^- \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the grid points that are inside of the grain return negative LS values (distances), while

those on the outside return positive ones; the points on the surface of the grain, belonging to the interface, all have LS values equal to 0.

2.2 Contact dynamics

Despite there being well known classical theoretical approaches, such as the ones provided by continuum mechanics and Cosserat Continuum Mechanics [1, 2, 18], they sometimes fail to fully capture the kinetics and kinematics at the grain-to-grain (microscopic) scale, which are key for understanding natural phenomena, such as landslides, liquefaction and shear-banding. In light of this problem, [8] introduced the DEM, a numerical method capable of simulating sets of particles by representing their topologies as perfect spheres. However, according to experimental works such as [6, 7], particle shape plays an enormous role in the mechanical response, fabric, and critical state, among other macroscopic properties of a granular material. Hence, in order to accurately capture the physics at the micro-scale, the irregular nature (shape and size) of the individual particles of a granular material must be taken into account. Despite this, obtaining a computational avatar of the geometry of a real particle while at the same time maintaining a feasible and efficient contact model is not an easy task. DEM schemes, such as sphere clumping [19], polyhedral [20], NURBS [21], and, most recently, super-quadrics [22], all deal with arbitrarily shaped particles. Nevertheless, these contact models are complex and computationally expensive. The 3DLS-DEM [9], on the other hand, is a generalization of the classical DEM that accurately captures the shape of the grain by making use of the LS functions as its geometric basis and whose efficiency is dependent on its contact algorithm,

Figure 2: Master-Slave contact model: given two grains, i and j (master and slave, respectively); contact is found by evaluating a master-particle interface point, p_i , on the slave-particle's LS function, ϕ_j .

3DLS-DEM employs a master-slave contact model to find the overlap, $\phi_j(p_i)$, and the normal vector, $\nabla\phi_j(p_i)$, at the contact point, p_i , through trilinear interpolation as depicted in Figure 2.

3 The Transient Heat Conduction Equation

The governing equation for transient heat conduction emerges from applying the energy balance and Fourier's law to an infinitesimal volume, which describes how heat diffuses through a solid and how its temperature changes over time [13].

3.1 Strong form

Assuming that the solid is made up of an isotropic material (i.e., its properties are the same in all directions), and that there is no internal heat generation, the governing equation results to be the PDE shown in eq.3, where α_d is the thermal diffusivity of the material, u is the temperature of said material, and t being the time.

Find $u = f(x, t) \in R$, such that,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \alpha_d \nabla^2 u = \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \\ q = \bar{q} \\ u = \bar{u} \\ u = u^* \\ \partial\Omega_u \cup \partial\Omega_q \equiv \partial\Omega \\ \partial\Omega_u \cap \partial\Omega_q \equiv \emptyset \end{array} \right. \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall x \in \Omega \subset R^3, \\ \forall t \in R^+, \\ \alpha_d = ctn \in R^+ \\ \forall x \in \partial\Omega_q \\ \forall t \in R^+ \cup \{0\} \\ \forall x \in \partial\Omega_u \\ \forall t > 0 \\ \forall x \in \Omega \\ t = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

In order to solve the PDE, it is necessary to specify initial conditions, u^* , and boundary conditions. In the heat transfer domain (see Figure 3), three types of boundary conditions can be applied. The first type, Dirichlet boundary conditions, \bar{u} , assume that the temperature values at the interface, $\partial\Omega_u$, are known. The second type, Neumann boundary conditions, assume that the derivative of the temperature, \bar{q} , is known at the interface, $\partial\Omega_q$. Finally, the third type combines both Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions.

Figure 3: Dirichlet, \bar{u} , and Neumann, \bar{q} , boundary conditions applied to the heat transfer domain of a grain.

While there do exist methods for finding an analytical solution for the governing equations (e.g., Fourier series, eigenfunction expansion, Green's Functions), most of these are limited to symmetrical shapes, such as slabs, spheres, or cylinders. However, real-world problems involve more complex geometries that have irregular boundaries at the heat transfer region, making it difficult to find analytical solutions [23]. It is possible, however, to find an approximate solution with the use of numerical methods, whose accuracy depends on the method and on the available computational power. Numerical methods, such as the Finite Difference Method (FDM), the Finite Volume Method (FVM), and the FEM, allow for obtaining approximations of unknown values at discrete points, called nodes: The last method, the FEM, is the most suitable for solving problems involving complex geometries [23]. So, in the present work, the application of the FEM towards solving the transient heat conduction equation is presented for a three-dimensional case. For this purpose, the basic FEM equations for three-dimensional linear tetrahedral elements are derived through the use of the Galerkin method [24].

3.2 Weak Form

In order to discretize the transient heat conduction equation using the FEM, it is necessary to convert the governing equation, eq.3, to its weak form. For this, eq.3 is multiplied by a weight function, $v(\mathbf{x})$, and then integrated over the entire domain Ω , resulting in eq.4.

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} v \, d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \alpha \nabla^2 u \cdot v \, d\Omega \quad (4)$$

Using integration by parts and applying the Green's identity on the right-hand side, the equation results in eq.5 where S is the domain's surface.

$$\int_{\Omega} \alpha \nabla^2 u \cdot v \, d\Omega = - \int_{\Omega} \alpha \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\Omega + \int_{\partial\Omega} \alpha \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} v \, dS \quad (5)$$

The weak form then becomes to eq.6, where $q = \alpha \frac{\partial T}{\partial n}$ is the prescribed Neumann heat flux on the boundary (Fourier's law).

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} v \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \alpha \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\Omega = \int_{\partial\Omega} q v \, dS \quad (6)$$

3.2.1 Mesh and shape functions

As mentioned before, most real-world problems involve complex geometries that cannot be solved analytically. Consequently, to obtain a numerical solution, discretization is crucial towards applying the FEM, since this process breaks down the domain, Ω , into smaller and simpler elements, $\Omega^{(e)}$ (e.g., triangles, tetrahedrons). In the present work, the geometrical basis that is chosen is the linear tetrahedral element, due to its versatility in capturing complex geometries. The temperature distribution for a given element, $\Omega^{(e)}$, within a cartesian coordinate system, (x, y, z) , with volume, $V^{(e)}$, is approximated with the use of linear tetrahedral element shape functions, $N_i^{(e)}$, presented in [14] (see eq.7). The coefficients, $(a_i^{(e)}, b_i^{(e)}, c_i^{(e)}, d_i^{(e)})$, and element's volume $V^{(e)}$ are defined in section 13. Each shape function corresponds to a single node and is equal to 1 at that node's location, while being equal to 0 at the location of every other node, while inside the element domain, the shape function takes on values between 0 and 1.

$$N_i^{(e)} = \frac{1}{6V^{(e)}} \left(a_i^{(e)} + b_i^{(e)}x + c_i^{(e)}y + d_i^{(e)}z \right) \quad (7)$$

3.3 Finite Element Discretization

This part of the discretization process assumes an approximate solution through shape functions N , where $v(\mathbf{x}) = N_i(\mathbf{x})$. Hence, the temperature u which is a function of position \mathbf{x} and time t results in eq.8.

$$u(\mathbf{x}, t) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N u_i(t)N_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad (8)$$

Then substituting the approximation into the weak form, it results in eq.9, where \mathbf{M}_{ij} , \mathbf{K}_{ij} and \mathbf{f}_i are the mass matrix, stiffness matrix and Neumann's boundary conditions vector (heat flow) respectively.

$$\sum_j \left(\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} N_j N_i d\Omega}_{\mathbf{M}_{ij}} \right) \frac{du_j}{dt} + \sum_j \left(\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \alpha \nabla N_j \cdot \nabla N_i d\Omega}_{\mathbf{K}_{ij}} \right) u_j = \underbrace{\int_{\partial\Omega} q N_i dS}_{\mathbf{f}_i} \quad (9)$$

3.3.1 Element Matrices

When time derivatives appear in mathematical problems (e.g., transient problems), some magnitudes that change over time are linked to the mass matrix. In terms of our study, the mass matrix represents the thermal inertia of the system, it captures how much energy is stored in each element due to its heat capacity and $N_j N_i$ reflects the coupling of nodal temperatures in storing thermal energy. Thus, the mass matrix for each discrete element could be approximated by eq. 10, where $\mathbf{J}^{(e)}$ is the element's jacobian (see section 13).

$$\mathbf{M}^{(e)} = \int_{\Omega} N_j N_i d\Omega \approx \frac{1}{60} |\mathbf{J}^{(e)}| \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ & 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ sym & & 1 & \frac{1}{2} \\ & & & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

On the other hand, the stiffness matrix models heat conduction (i.e., thermal diffusion), it reflects the ability of the material to resist temperature gradients. Larger values of thermal conductivity κ result in larger stiffness matrix entries. It essentially controls how temperature spreads spatially across the domain. Thus, the stiffness matrix for each discrete element could be approximated by eq. 11, where its coefficients ($K_{11}, K_{12}, \dots, K_{43}, K_{44}$) as well as the element's volume $V^{(e)}$ are defined in section 13.

$$\mathbf{K}^{(e)} = \int_{\Omega} \alpha \nabla N_j \cdot \nabla N_i d\Omega \approx \frac{\alpha_d}{36V^{(e)}} \begin{pmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} & K_{14} \\ & K_{22} & K_{23} & K_{24} \\ sym & & K_{33} & K_{34} \\ & & & K_{44} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Finally, the Neumann boundary vector accounts for external heat fluxes entering or leaving the domain through its boundaries. It directly adds or removes energy at the boundary nodes, depending on the sign and magnitude of the heat flux. Thus, the Neumann's boundary vector for each discrete element could be approximated by eq.12, where \bar{q} is the heat flux rate.

$$\mathbf{f}^{(e)} = \int_{\partial\Omega} qN_i dS \approx -\bar{q} \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{6} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

3.4 The Transient Heat Conduction Equation in its matrix Form

Up to this point, for any given domain, Ω , the space discretization of the transient heat conduction equation is carried out through the use of the Galerkin-FEM, resulting in eq.13, where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix, $\mathbf{f}(t)$ is the boundary conditions vector, and $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is the temperature distribution vector.

$$\mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{f}(t) \quad (13)$$

However, since the upper dot of $\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t)$ indicates the derivation of the temperature with respect to time, the integration of $\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t)$ must be addressed at some point. A popular scheme for integration with respect to time is the so-called θ -method. According to [25], when dealing with a time derivative in a finite difference case, by taking values of $\theta = 0, 1, 1/2$, it is possible to obtain either the forward Euler, backward Euler, or Crank-Nicholson method, respectively. To be consistent with the explicit integration of the motion equations proposed in [21], the appropriate method for integrating $\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t)$ is with the use of the forward Euler, which is first-order accurate with respect to Δt .

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) = \frac{\mathbf{u}_{t+1} - \mathbf{u}_t}{\Delta t} + \mathbf{O}(\Delta t) \quad (14)$$

Thus, by replacing the finite difference, eq.14, into eq.13, and then solving for \mathbf{u}_{t+1} by applying matrix operations, the equation for calculating the temperature distribution vector results in eq.15.

$$\mathbf{u}_{t+1} = (\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{K}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_t + \Delta t \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{f}_t \quad (15)$$

At this moment, it is important to point out that the matrices \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{M} do not vary over time, meaning that the terms that multiply \mathbf{u}_t and \mathbf{f}_t , can be condensed into the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} ,

respectively, resulting in that eq.15 is restated as eq.16.

$$\mathbf{u}_{t+1} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{f}_t \quad (16)$$

Finally, the average grain temperature distribution is calculated following the eq.17.

$$\bar{u}_t^g = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{nodes}} \frac{\mathbf{u}_t^g(i)}{N_{nodes}} \quad (17)$$

4 The 3DLS-DEM + FEM for multi-body heat conduction

In the previous section, a fully detailed description of the discretization of the transient heat conduction equation through the FEM was presented, eventually resulting in its matrix form (eq. 16). Thus, the temperature diffusion within the volume of an individual grain for any given initial and boundary conditions is solved using this matrix equation. However, even though the FEM is the most suitable method for solving the transient heat conduction problem, when multiple bodies are involved the FEM lacks in efficiency. This is due to that contact detection between bodies implies solving a complex geometric problem [26], making the implementation of the FEM computationally expensive.

When sets consisting of hundreds to thousands of particles are to be simulated, DEM schemes are more suitable. Despite these advantages, the DEM's efficiency also depends on the contact algorithm. The method that allows for simulating arbitrarily shaped particles while maintaining an efficient contact algorithm is the 3DLS-DEM. Therefore, in the present study the mechanical interaction between grains (i.e., dynamics and kinematics) is solved using the 3DLS-DEM, while the temperature diffusion described by the transient heat conduction equation is solved with the use of the FEM.

4.1 Bridging the 3DLS-DEM and the FEM

Aside from simplifying the domain, Ω , discretization is also essential for the FEM, since it allows for converting complex PDEs into a system of algebraic equations that can be solved numerically. Also,

the choice of a discretization method and the quality of the resulting mesh are critical factors that influence the effectiveness, numerical stability and accuracy of the FEM [27, 28]. Still, breaking down an irregular shape into simpler components is not a trivial task since it implies finding a unique way to connect a set of points into groups of elements that, as a sum, constitute the original irregular shape. Triangulation (2D) or tetrahedralization (3D) methods (e.g. Delaunay's) allow for flexible, unique, and efficient meshing and are also versatile across various applications [29, 30].

Figure 4: Tetrahedralization process: a) a grain's LS interface. b) the grain's surface triangulation. c) the grain's volume tetrahedralization.

The inherent advantages of LS functions (see eq.2) for representing 3D irregular shapes are leveraged for also carrying out the meshing of the grains (see Figure 4 a). The process consists of first placing a set of points (nodes) on the interface, $\partial\Omega$, (i.e., level zero of the LS function). Then, a Delaunay triangulation is applied to connect the nodes into a set of triangles, which leads to a discrete representation of the LS surface (see Figure 4 b). However, since a 3D heat conduction problem is presented, the discretization of the grain volume, and not just of the surface, is necessary. Given that Delaunay's method ensures the existence and uniqueness of the surface triangulation, the nodes of all the surface triangles can be connected to a common point in the center that coincides

with the grain’s centroid. This results in a tetrahedral mesh of the grain volume (see Figure 4 c), which is also unique. The discretization process is stored in a matrix (connectivity table), whose values are the indexes of the nodes connected together to an element. This connectivity table allows for assembling the global stiffness, \mathbf{K} , mass, \mathbf{M} , and boundary conditions, \mathbf{f} , matrices.

4.2 Multi-body heat conduction scheme

As previously stated in section 3, for a given domain, Ω , three types of boundary conditions can be applied: Dirichlet, Neumann or the combination of the two. Dirichlet boundary conditions imply specifying the nodes where the temperature is known onto the vector \mathbf{u}_t from eq.16 and then reducing the matrix system. On the other hand, Neumann boundary conditions imply modifying the global boundary conditions vector, \mathbf{f}_t , by specifying in it on which element boundaries the temperature derivative is known. Given that, in our approach, the dynamics and kinetics of the grains are being considered, the contact points between the grains will likely change over time, making Neumann boundary conditions more suitable.

The conduction heat transfer mechanism is the transfer of heat through molecular excitement within a material without bulk motion of the matter. It mostly occurs in stationary media, such as fluids at rest or solids. Particularly in solids, it is mainly due to the combination of lattice vibrations of the molecules and to the energy transport by free electrons [31]. Fourier’s law governs conduction heat transfer through a material. In considering the simplest scenario (one-dimensional), a wall of area A of infinitesimal thickness, dx , Fourier’s law states that the rate of heat transfer, \bar{q} , through a material is directly proportional to the negative gradient of the temperature and to the area through which the heat flows, resulting in eq.18, where k the thermal conductivity constant.

$$\bar{q} = -kA \frac{du}{dx} \quad (18)$$

Now, let us consider a scenario involving two bodies, each one with a given initial temperature. The way in which they conduct heat between each other is through contact. Thus, at the contact points, there exists heat flow due to the temperature gradient there. Such heat flow must be prescribed at the boundary, which implies imposing Neumann boundary conditions onto the transient heat conduction equation of each body.

4.3 Grain-to-grain contact

In order to calculate the heat flow at the contact point between two grains, the efficiency of the master-slave contact model is considered. The mechanical interaction in the 3DLS-DEM is driven by normal contacts that are handled through a master-slave contact model [9], whereby control points are seeded onto the surfaces of the master and slave grain shapes that are implicitly embedded in their LS functions. Hence, to leverage the efficiency of the master-slave contact model, in the presented approach, the control points are placed onto the element faces formed by the nodes (1,2,3) as depicted in Figure 4 c). Thus, given any two grains, with one designated as the master grain, i , and the other designated as the slave grain, j , with their respective temperature distributions having been calculated with the use of eq.16, the master-slave contact model identifies an element, $\Omega^{i(e)}$, with a temperature of $u^{i(e)}$ from the master grain as being in contact with a slave grain that has an average temperature of \bar{u}^j . Additionally, according to [9], the 3DLS-DEM employs a linear elastic contact model, meaning that small deformations are permitted. In other words, the overlap, Δx , represents the deformation at the contact point.

Figure 5: Master-slave heat conduction contact model.

Since the temperature distributions of the master and slave grains are known, and the materials of the two grains are the same, and the deformations due to contact are sufficiently small, eq.18 can therefore be used as a basis to calculate the heat flow at the contact point. The heat flow, \bar{q}_t , at

the time step t at the point p_i is computed following the eq.19, where k is the thermal conductivity, Δx is the overlap, $A^{i(e)}$ is the facet area of the e -th element of the master grain surface area, $u_t^{i(e)}$ is the temperature of the e -th element of the master grain at the time step t , and \bar{u}_{t-1}^j is the average temperature of the slave grain at the time step $t - 1$.

$$\bar{q}_t = -kA^{i(e)} \frac{(u_t^{i(e)} - \bar{u}_{t-1}^j)}{\Delta x} \quad (19)$$

Considering that the master-slave contact scheme is used, Neumann boundary conditions are imposed on the elements of the master grain that are in contact with a slave grain. Thus, the element's boundary condition vector, $\mathbf{f}_{123}^{(e)}$, is calculated with the use of eq.20, where, $\mathbf{J}^{(e)}$ is the element's Jacobian and the vector (1,1,1,0) is defined by the boundary conditions that are imposed on the master-grain element facet which is composed of the nodes (1,2 and 3).

$$\mathbf{f}_{123}^{(e)} = -\bar{q}_t \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{6} \left\{ \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad (20)$$

Given that the master grain can be in contact with multiple slave grains, all local boundary conditions computed at the contact points must be specified on the global boundary conditions vector, \mathbf{f} , of the master grain. This process consists of identifying the indexes of the elements where the local boundary conditions are imposed and then using the master-grain connectivity table to reassemble the global boundary conditions vector, \mathbf{f} , which is initially filled with zeros. Subsequently, \mathbf{f} is used to update the master-grain temperature distribution.

4.4 Grain-wall contact

In this study, not only is the grain-to-grain heat conduction considered, but also the grain-to-wall interaction. For this purpose, to be able use eq.18 as a basis for calculating the heat flow at the contact point between a grain and a wall, the wall must be assumed as being of the same material as the grains. In this case, according to the master-slave scheme, the grain is considered as the master, and the wall is considered as the slave. Thus, eq.19 then becomes eq.21, where u^{wall} is the

wall temperature.

$$\bar{q}_t = -kA^{i(e)} \frac{(u_t^{i(e)} - u_{t-1}^{wall})}{\Delta x} \quad (21)$$

5 Thermal grain dialation (expansion-contraction)

The main reason that materials expand or contract due to the effect of a temperature variation is that when the atomic vibrations (phonons) increase in amplitude, the energy is minimized at greater atomic spacings [32]. This concept is described by the Gruneisen relation [33], which states that the thermal expansion of a Debye solid is proportional to the specific heat and the constant of proportionality (thermal expansion coefficient), which is practically independent of the temperature.

Volumetric thermal expansion is a phenomenon widely known due to its enormous impact on numerous engineering applications. In substances that have interfaces between different materials, such as in composites, coatings, and joints, stresses may be generated at these interfaces due to a thermal expansion mismatch. Moreover, a critical limitation on the reliability and performance of modern electronic circuits is the stress caused by thermal expansion. For this reason, temperature cycling and temperature shock are standard methods of evaluating new products and processes.

In the present work, the grain domain is assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic. According to [34], for isotropic materials, the thermal expansion tensor is represented by eq.22, which is an isotropic second-order tensor, where α_l is the linear thermal expansion coefficient and $\mathbf{1}$ is the identity matrix.

$$\mathbf{E} = \alpha_l \mathbf{1} \quad (22)$$

Moreover, the constitutive equation for strain, where \mathbf{C}_{isoT}^e is the isothermal elastic tensor, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, and Δu the temperature variation is eq.23.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{C}_{isoT}^e : \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \Delta u \mathbf{E} \quad (23)$$

Assuming that the strain is driven only by thermal changes ($\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0}$), eq.23 results in eq.24.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \alpha_l \Delta u \mathbf{1} \quad (24)$$

From eq.24, an expression for the expected volume of a solid after being subjected to a temperature variation, Δu , can be derived, resulting in eq.25, where V_o is the initial volume of the solid and α_v is the volumetric thermal expansion coefficient (i.e., $3\alpha_l$).

$$V_t = (1 + \alpha_v \Delta u) V_o \quad (25)$$

5.1 Solving for grain volumetric expansion with the use of the LS functions, the Grain Swelling Function

As previously mentioned, materials expand or contract due to the effects of a temperature variation. Thus, to include the volumetric thermal expansion phenomenon into the 3DLS-DEM+FEM model, the finite element mesh, control points, and LS function of each grain must be modified. Dealing with the control points and the vertices of the finite element mesh is relatively easy: it is enough to apply a transformation (eq.26) to the reference configuration of the i -th control point or vertex, \mathbf{p}_i .

$$\mathbf{p}'_i = (\mathbf{1} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \mathbf{p}_i \quad (26)$$

On the other hand, in order to manipulate the LS function, the definitions described in section 2 are taken into account. For this case, the objective is to displace the LS function interface, $\partial\Omega$ (see Figure 6), inwards or outwards. following the volumetric thermal expansion-contraction theory.

Figure 6: A digital grain LS function (a) 3D, b) a 2D slice), before and after being dilated 10% above its initial volume.

Considering that the LS function is a scalar field and in accordance with its definition in eq.2, the sum of tiny increments to the LS function displaces the interface, $\partial\Omega$, inwards, while subtraction displaces it outwards. Since the strain change is driven by the temperature, variation, Δu , the process of modifying the LS function consists of summing $\alpha_l \Delta u$ increments until the LS volume converges to the volume established by eq.25. This is done to predict how many increments must be summed and to make the process physically consistent with the theory.

The process for manipulating the LS function (the dilation function) is detailed in pseudo-code 1. First, the theoretical volume, V_t , is calculated according to the eq.25, taking into account that for an isotropic material α_v is $3\alpha_l$. Second, the relative error of the LS function volume at the i -th iteration, $V_{ls}^{(i)}$, with respect to the theoretical volume, V_t , is calculated. Inside of a while loop, the following process continues while the error is bigger than a specified tolerance. Third, $V_{ls}^{(i)}$ is reinitialized to zero at each new iteration. Fourth, since the LS function is stored as a third-order tensor, the code iterates through the $(x,y$ and $z)$ directions in order to sum the $\alpha_l L \Delta u$ increment to the LS function at the i -th iteration, $\phi^{(i)}$. Then the volume of the i -th iteration, $V_{ls}^{(i)}$, is calculated with the use of the smooth Heavy-Side function eq.27. After this, the code returns again to test

the condition of the while loop.

$$H(\phi, \epsilon) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \phi < -\epsilon \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\phi}{\epsilon} + \frac{\sin(\frac{\pi\phi}{\epsilon})}{\pi} \right) & \text{if } -\epsilon < \phi < \epsilon \\ 1 & \text{if } \phi > \epsilon \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

Pseudo-code 1 Level Set Function update due to thermal expansion-contraction

Input: $\phi^{(i)}$ (Level set function of the i-th grain)
 ϵ (smoothness parameter)
 α_l (linear thermal expansion coefficient)
 α_v (volumetric thermal expansion coefficient)
 tol (algorithm tolerance)
 $[xDim, yDim, zDim]$ (dimensions of LS function)
 Δu (temperature variation through time)
 V_o (initial grain volume)
 L (Level set grid spacing)

Procedure:

```

 $V_t \leftarrow (1 + \alpha_v \Delta u) V_o$ 
while  $|V_{ls}^{(i)} - V_t| / V_t > tol$  do
     $V_{ls}^{(i)} \leftarrow 0$ 
    for  $x = 1 : xDim$  do
        for  $y = 1 : yDim$  do
            for  $z = 1 : zDim$  do
                 $\phi^{(i)}(x, y, z) \leftarrow \phi^{(i)}(x, y, z) - \alpha_l L \Delta u$ 
                 $V_{ls}^{(i)} \leftarrow V_{ls}^{(i)} + H(\phi^{(i)}(x, y, z), \epsilon)$ 
            end for
        end for
    end for
end while

```

The entire described process is demonstrated through a benchmark test in which the smallest and largest grains of a sample were used. Both grains were artificially dilated until reaching to 10% of volumetric strain. The decimal logarithm of the error vs the number of iterations is depicted in Figure 7, where it is observed that, for the smallest grain (green line), it takes 19 iterations for the error to converge to the desired tolerance (red dotted line), while for the largest one (blue line), 47 iterations were necessary. However, it is important to remark that a 10% increase of volumetric strain falls into the non-elastic regime which is beyond the scope of this study, but is useful for demonstrating the capabilities of the method.

Figure 7: The smallest and largest grains of the packing sample diluted to 10 % above their original volumes.

6 Coupling the 3DLS-DEM, the FEM and the Grain Swelling Function

Now with the 3DLS-DEM, the FEM, and the grain dilation methods all having been explained up to this point, the coupling algorithm can be described in detail using a flow diagram (Fig. 8). The required grain data for the 3DLS-DEM, including the positions of the centers of mass, orientations in space (quaternions), inertial properties, the grain meshes, and grain LS functions are all given as inputs. At $t = 0$, the FEM global matrices: the stiffness, \mathbf{K} , mass. \mathbf{M} , and the boundary conditions, \mathbf{f} , are assembled using the grain meshes. After that, the boundary and initial conditions for the FEM model are given. The simulation begins by solving the FEM equation; from this process, the grain average temperatures are obtained. Then, the temperature of each grain is passed to the dilation function. The grains come out of the dilation function with new configurations (either expanded or contracted) and then the 3DLS-DEM performs the contact computations with the grains in these new configurations.

Figure 8: Flow diagram of the simulation.

7 Benchmark numerical testing

In this section, a test on a cubic sample composed of 29 grains is presented. This test case is realized to demonstrate the model’s capabilities and the effects of heat conduction on the mechanical behavior of granular media by means of a computer simulation. The mechanical interaction is performed employing the contact algorithm and the principal body-fixed frame movement introduced by [9], while the positions and rotations of the grains are updated following the time integration scheme as in [21]. For applying hydrostatic confinement to the sample, a fixed wall scheme is used. The grain shapes used for all tests thorough the present work is martian regolith simulant from a real soil sample that was scanned through 3D X-ray Computed Tomography and was processed following [35]. However, even though martian regolith is a type of sand, in our approach, the material itself of the grains is assumed to be made of iron in order to obtain a faster convergence to the prescribed temperatures.

The simulation parameters needed to solve the contact dynamics, such as the normal elastic, K_n , tangential elastic, K_s , and interparticle friction, μ , coefficients, are shown in Table 1. Once again, to reduce computational costs, the grain material was decided as being made of iron, and as such, the thermal properties of the grains are also shown in Table 1.

Simulation Parameter	Value
Normal elastic, K_n	1.7e5 [N/m]
Tangential elastic, K_s	1.53e5 [N/m]
Interparticle friction coefficient, μ	0.65
Density, ρ	7874 [kg/m ³]
Thermal conductivity, k	79.75 [W/m · K]
Thermal diffusivity, α_d	22.8 [m ² /s]
Thermal expansion coefficient, α_l	12.1 x 10 ⁻⁶ [K ⁻¹]
Time step increment, Δt	1 x 10 ⁻⁵ [s]
Confinement pressure	0.5 [kg _f /m ²]

Table 1: Simulation parameters for solving the contact dynamics and the heat conduction equation using the FEM.

Furthermore, it is necessary to point out that for our grain dilation model, we make the following assumptions:

- The grain material is assumed to be isotropic, homogeneous, and thermo-elastic.
- Only the conduction heat transfer mechanism is considered.
- At any given time step, the sample container walls are subjected to minor increments in temperature, so there should not be any thermal shock between the grains and the walls.
- The grain mesh quality is sufficient enough to ensure numerical stability to assure a solution of the FEM equations.
- The temperatures imposed on the sample container walls do not surpass the range of temperatures for the solid phase of the grain material (i.e., iron).
- The time increment, Δt , has been chosen to ensure stability for the numerical solutions while maintaining a manageable computational cost.

7.1 Sample Container Walls

The grains are confined inside of a container whose walls are each defined by a plane and whose normal vectors point inward as in a convex hull system. The forces and dynamics at any contact point between a grain and a wall are computed following the equations presented in [9]. In addition, in our approach, the heat flows from the walls to the grains through contact points following the master-slave contact model described in section 4. The wall temperature varies over time following eq.28, where u_a is the initial temperature, u_b is the final temperature, t is the time step, and t_{total} is the total number of time steps.

$$u_t^{wall} = u_a + t \cdot \left(\frac{u_b - u_a}{t_{total}} \right) \quad (28)$$

7.2 Benchmark test: 29 grains

For this test, 29 grains are confined inside of a fixed-wall cubic container. The amount of grains as well as the sample dimensions are listed in Table 2. This particular geometry (a cube) was chosen in order to match the directions of the components of the Cauchy stress tensor [36] in a cartesian coordinate system. As shown in Figure 9, the normal components of the stress tensor are depicted in red, while the tangential components are in green.

Figure 9: The cubic container, along with the normal (red arrows) and tangential (green arrows) components of the stress tensor.

Sample parameter	Value
Type of sample container walls	Fixed walls
Number of grains	29
Number of sample container walls	6
Sample container size	1.4938 x 1.4938 x 1.4938 [mm]

Table 2: Parameters of the 29 grain sample used for this benchmark test.

The first stage (confinement stage) of the simulation takes 1.1 seconds (110k time steps); during this stage, hydrostatic (isotropic) compression is applied to the sample. This is done by moving the walls inwards, which enables for the sample to reach average hydrostatic conditions. In this stage, the grains and walls remain in thermal equilibrium at a temperature of 298K. Once the confinement process is complete, the second stage (the heating process) takes place between 1.1 to 11.1 seconds, during which the wall temperature (blue line in Figure 10) is increased from 298K to 353K following eq.28. The third stage (stabilization) occurs from 11.1 to 21.1 seconds, where the wall temperature is maintained at 353K. As the wall temperature increases over time, the difference in temperature between the walls and the grains induces a heat flow into the grains, gradually increasing the average packing temperature (magenta line in Figure 10). In an ideal case, it would be expected that the average packing temperature would exhibit linear behavior, equaling the wall temperature. However, given that the grains expand or contract under the effect of temperature variation, the contact points between the grains and the walls and between the grains themselves vary over time due to rearrangements within the sample. This leads the average packing temperature to exhibit nonlinear behavior.

Figure 10: Evolution of the wall prescribed temperature (blue line) and the average packing temperature (magenta line) over time.

Temperature fits into the definition of a scalar field since at any given location, it is described by a single value, not having any particular direction. So, a good way to represent the temperature distribution over the grain surface at any given instant is through a color heat map. Thus, each element facet on the grain surface is painted with a color according to its temperature, where redder colors represent higher temperatures and bluer colors represent lower temperatures, on an interval ranging from 298K to 353K, as depicted by the color bar in Figure 11. As can be seen in Figures 10 and 11, at the beginning of the simulation (point a)) the 29 grains are in thermal equilibrium with the walls of the container, at 298K. From point a) to point c), passing through point b), the average packing temperature diverges from the wall temperature, mainly due to the fact that the heat conduction between the walls and the grains is not instantaneous and to that the contact points between the grains vary over time. However, from point c) to point d), the average packing temperature begins to converge to the wall temperature.

Figure 11: The stages of heat distribution within the cubic container. The color map represents the temperature range, with the hotter regions in red and the colder regions in blue.

As can be seen in Figure 12, the evolution over time of the average percentual volume change of the packing exhibits the same behavior as the average packing temperature (compare with Figure 10). Since materials expand or contract due to the effect of temperature variations, as per eq.25,

the relationship between the change in volume and the temperature is directly proportional, in line with the theory described in section 5.

Figure 12: Evolution of average percentual volume change over time. This result indicates that the change in volume and temperature are directly proportional.

The average stress tensor reflects the main response of the grain volume change due to the effect of temperature variation. The average Cauchy stress tensor components are computed based on the inter-particle contact forces scheme presented in [37]. The stress tensor component evolution over time and its relationship with the temperature are depicted in Figure 13. Stress tensor normal (σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} , and σ_{zz}) and tangential components (σ_{yz} , σ_{xz} , and σ_{xy}), exhibit noisy behavior as the wall temperature increases from 298K to 322.12K (point a and point b, respectively, in Figure 13 (iii) and (iv)). This implies that grain rearrangements are taking place within the sample. The normal components from point b to point c, this last point being at 348.83K (Figure 13 (iii) and (iv)), exhibit an increasing monotonic behavior, reaching a maximum of 0.73 in the σ_{xx} component at 7.92 seconds.

A considerable decay is exhibited by σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} components accompanied by an immediate increase after 7.92 seconds, showing that major rearrangements took place in the direction of the x and y axis. Moreover, the tangential components exhibit similar behavior as the normals, but in their case, the σ_{xy} component shows a major gap in comparison with the σ_{yz} and σ_{xz} components,

implying that friction is higher in the x - y plane.

From point c) to point d), this last point being at 352.53K (Figure 13 (iii) and (iv)), the grain temperature gradient is not enough to induce volumetric changes, since the average packing temperature begins to converge to the wall temperature. Similarly, the normal and tangential components begin to converge and remain constant over time.

Figure 13: The Cauchy stress tensor component evolution over time and the effect of temperature variation on them. (i) the evolution of the stress tensor normal components (σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and σ_{zz}) over time, (ii) the evolution of the stress tangential components (σ_{yz} , σ_{xz} , and σ_{xy}) over time. (iii) the effect of temperature variation on the stress tensor normal components, (iv) the effect of temperature variation on the stress tangential components.

8 High-performance computing-based numerical testing

In this section, the optimization of our 3DLS-DEM + FEM model through the use of parallelization libraries is presented, followed by its application on a clay stone specimen use-case scenario, to exhibit the real implications of the heat conduction and volume expansion phenomena.

The 3DLS-DEM scheme can simulate thousands of arbitrarily shaped particles, however, this

task demands several orders of magnitude greater of computational resources than if spherical particles were involved. For comparison, according to [38], the computational load for simulating 488 thousand poly-ellipsoid particles is equivalent to simulating 122 million spherical particles (250x). Similarly, the 3DLS-DEM faces a bottleneck related to the contact model and particle amount. Thus, 3DLS-DEM should be carried out in parallel when dealing with thousands of particles.

In the approach proposed in this manuscript, the advantages of parallelization libraries, such as the Open Multi-Processing (openMP) and Message-Passing Interface (MPI), are considered, not just to compute the mechanical forces, but also for the heat conduction between grains that follows the master-slave contact model presented in section 4. Besides this, another crucial step in 3DLS-DEM is the integration of variables over time. Here, the coupled 3DLS-DEM + FEM encounters another important bottleneck. Integrating the motion equations implies solving matrix operations in which, at the most, 3 by 1 vectors and 3 by 3 matrices are involved [21]. For this purpose, the linear algebra library Eigen is suitable. However, integrating the discretized heat conduction equation by the FEM implies multiplying and summing large-sized matrices, for which the Eigen library results in being very inefficient. Therefore, the computation of the grain temperature distribution (eq.16) must be optimized. This optimization is made possible through leveraging specific features of Intel CPUs, through the MKL, as well as by integrating the CUDA, which is generally known as being very efficient in computing dense matrix operations.

8.1 The Math Kernel Library (MKL)

Given that the heaviest stage of the simulation involves matrix operations, the most straightforward optimization that would not require modifications to the base code is the integration of the Intel’s MKL. Moreover, the algorithm primarily relies on the Eigen library, which has supported MKL optimization since version 3.1 [39]. All of this clearly establishes that the first step to be taken is the integration of MKL.

The Math Kernel Library (MKL) [40] is an optimized library developed by Intel for high-performance mathematical computations. It implements the BLAS and LAPACK specifications, which define a set of basic linear algebra operations, such as matrix multiplication, factorization, and system solvers. Moreover, it is designed to leverage specific features of Intel CPUs,

using CPU-specific instructions to optimize numerical operations. Integrating this library is relatively straightforward, as Eigen, being compatible with MKL, allows for defining a constant, `EIGEN_USE_MKL_ALL`, and linking to it during compilation. This approach facilitates the optimization of calculating eq.16 and enhances the overall performance of the simulation.

8.2 The Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA)

The integration of CUDA is aimed at the computation of eq.16, in order to offload onto the GPU, the matrix calculations performed for obtaining the temperature distribution of each grain; in this way leveraging the high computing capacity and specialization of graphics cards for solving large numerical and matrix calculations. For carrying out the integration of CUDA, modifications were necessary for loading the data of each grain and calculating the temperature distribution for each individual grain. For loading of the matrix data, the constructor of the grains was modified in order to allocate memory on the GPU and copy to it the necessary data for the calculations, including the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , matrix \mathbf{u}_t , and the vector \mathbf{f}_t . First, the memory is allocated through the `cudaMalloc` command and then these data are transferred one by one from the CPU to the GPU to have them available when they are required.

Since the operation that has the most significant impact on the simulation scheme is the computation of eq.16, it was decided to divide this operation into two stages for better leveraging the functionalities provided by CUDA. First, the multiplication, $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u}_t$, was carried out, then later the multiplication, $\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{f}_t$, is done and then the resulting vectors were added. To enhance the performance of this operation, the `cublasDgemv` function [41] is applied; this function, based on matrix-vector multiplication, is provided by CUDA and is part of NVIDIA’s linear algebra library (cuBlas).

By implementing eq.29, `cublasDgemv` leverages the architecture of the GPU to perform these calculations in parallel, thereby improving the efficiency of both the matrix and vector operations.

$$\mathbf{y} = \alpha op(\mathbf{A}_{temp}) \cdot \mathbf{x} + \beta \mathbf{y} \quad (29)$$

This function performs the matrix-vector operation, specifically with double-precision floating point arithmetic, where \mathbf{A}_{temp} is a matrix, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are each vectors, and α and β are scalars. It is essentially a linear combination of the columns of the matrix \mathbf{A}_{temp} with the coefficients of

the vector \mathbf{x} scaled by α , added to the vector \mathbf{y} scaled by β , making it a standard Level 2 BLAS operation for matrix-vector multiplication and addition. In the first stage, we set α equal to 1, matrix \mathbf{A}_{temp} equal to \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{x} equal to vector \mathbf{u}_t , and β equal to 0, allowing the CUDA implementation to ignore the addition and perform only the multiplication $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u}_t$. The result is directly stored in the vector \mathbf{u}_t .

For the second stage, we execute the same operation, but for the matrix \mathbf{B} and the vector \mathbf{f}_t , setting α equal to 1, \mathbf{A}_{temp} equal to the matrix \mathbf{B} , and \mathbf{x} equal to the vector \mathbf{f}_t , and take advantage of the operation to set β equal to 1 and \mathbf{y} equal to \mathbf{u}_t , with this last vector containing the result of the previous operation. This enables us to obtain the final result by first multiplying $\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{f}_t$, and then adding this to the previous result stored in \mathbf{u}_t . This approach achieves a minor optimization in calculating the temperature of each grain, leveraging the parallel processing capability of the GPU through the cublasDgemv function that is provided by CUDA.

8.3 Test under drained conditions: 100 grain specimen

The study of the response of a drained specimen of Opalinus clay introduced by [16], consists of subjecting a specimen to thermal cycles ranging from 298.15K to 353.15K under mean stress conditions inside of a hollow cylinder apparatus, where, in order to apply the heating and cooling process, the specimen is submerged in a temperature-controlled water bath. In the study, the effect of temperature variation on the expansion-contraction of the specimen (i.e., volumetric strain) is studied in detail.

In the present approach, a fixed convex hull system is used for simulating the container. Here, the impact of temperature variation on the stress is studied rather than on the volumetric strain. To match the geometry of the hollow cylinder apparatus presented in [16], 100 grains are confined in a cylindrical container (see Figure 14) whose dimensions and characteristics are shown in Table 3, and the grain properties as well as the simulation parameters are the same as those used for the cube in section 7.

Sample parameter	Value
Sample container walls	Fixed walls
Number of grains	100
Number of sample container walls	23
Sample container radius	2.0539 [mm]
Sample container height	1.7987 [mm]

Table 3: Parameters used to test the effect of temperature variation on a 100 grain sample.

In order to replicate the experiment proposed by [16], the heating-cooling cycles are applied to the fixed walls following eq.28, which implies imposing Dirichlet boundary conditions globally as depicted in Figure 14. Nevertheless, Neumann boundary conditions are applied locally following the grain-to-wall heat conduction model described in section 4,

Figure 14: Dirichlet boundary conditions applied to the fixed walls of the 100 grain sample container.

As depicted in Figure 15, in the first stage, from 0 to 5 seconds (500k time steps), the wall temperature begins at 298K and remains constant until the sample reaches hydrostatic conditions (i.e., the sample reaches the confinement pressure). During this stage, the grains are in thermal equilibrium, and the confinement is carried out by pushing the walls inwards. Next, the heating stage (point a) to b)) takes place from 5 to 15 seconds (1 million time steps). As can be seen in

Figure 15, the average packing temperature (red line) exhibits non-linear behavior, unlike the wall temperature (blue line). That is until it reaches 340.19K, where the wall temperature meanwhile is at 353K. During the stage from 15 to 27 seconds (points b) to c)), the wall temperature remains constant, and the average packing temperature begins to converge to the prescribed temperature of the walls until they reach 350.41K. It is important to point out that the time interval chosen for this stage (from point b) to point c)) is based on the previous experiment presented in section 7, in which the average packing temperature converged relatively more quickly to the wall temperature, to the point that there was no significant difference after a couple of seconds (see Figure 10). The cooling stage (from point c) to point d)) takes place from 27 to 37 seconds, where the wall temperature is lowered from 353K back down to the initial temperature of 298K. In the course of this stage, the average packing temperature again exhibits non-linear behavior until reaching 310.94 K; its descending trajectory is clearly different from the heating stage trajectory. Finally, in the last stage from 37 to 49 seconds, the wall temperature remains constant at 298K, and the average packing temperature converges to this temperature until reaching 300.6K.

Figure 15: Evolution of the prescribed wall temperature (blue line) and the average packing temperature (red line) over time.

The evolution of the temperature over time, depicted in Figure 15, can also be observed through

a color heat map (Figure 16), where the surfaces of the grains exhibit warmer or cooler color patterns depending on their temperature state. The colors represent temperatures ranging from 298K to 353K. Through the representation of the packing (specimen) temperature distribution depicted in Figure 16, it is possible to identify how heat flows from the walls to the packing.

Figure 16: The stages of heat distribution within the packing. The color map represents the temperature range, with the hotter regions in red and the colder regions in blue.

As described in section 5, changes in temperature induce strain and according to eq.24, the strain is proportional to the temperature variation. That is, the average packing volume change is expected to exhibit the same behavior as the average packing temperature (see Figure 17 a)). The average volume change increases due to the effect of temperature variation until it reaches a maximum of 0.19%. At this point, the porosity (see Figure 17 b)) reaches its minimum as the packing becomes denser. When the temperature decreases, the average volume change and porosity return to their initial state values.

Figure 17: The effect of temperature variation on the volume and porosity of the 100 grain sample. As the volume increases due to thermal expansion, the porosity decreases due to the pack becoming denser. When the temperature decreases, the average volume and porosity converge to their initial state values.

The volumetric expansion and contraction of the grains due to the effect of temperature variation induces rearrangements within the packing. These rearrangements cause the contact points to vary over time, and consequently, the average stress tensor changes over time as well. Since the geometry of the sample packing is cylindrical, it is not convenient to analyze the evolution over time of each component of the stress tensor as was done for the cubic packing presented in section 7. Instead, for the packing geometry presented in this section, it is more convenient to decompose the stress tensor, σ , into its spherical component, σ^{sph} , and deviatoric component, σ^{dev} , following the process presented in [34] (see eq.30).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{sph} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{dev} = \frac{\text{Tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})}{3} \mathbf{1} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{dev} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{dev} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \frac{\text{Tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})}{3} \mathbf{1} \end{array} \right. \quad (30)$$

By decomposing the stress tensor, it is possible to calculate the variables p and s , which are fundamental for describing the state of stress in the sample (eq. 31). The mean pressure, p , represents the isotropic or hydrostatic stress (i.e., that acts equally in all directions). On the other hand, s , represents the deviatoric stress that induces deformations on the material in different directions.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} p = \frac{\text{Tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})}{3} \\ s = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{dev} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{dev})} \end{array} \right. \quad (31)$$

In particular, p controls the volume of the material, which affects phenomena such as compaction and dilation. Figure 18 shows the relationship between p and the temperature in the sample. The hydrostatic stress, p , starts at $0.483[\frac{kg_f}{cm^2}]$ (confinement pressure). As the temperature increases, p shows a monotonic growth, which corresponds to the thermal expansion of the grains. p then reaches a maximum of $0.524[\frac{kg_f}{cm^2}]$, corresponding to the maximum temperature of the packing, at $350.41K$. When the temperature decreases, p decreases due to the thermal contraction of the grains. The behavior is almost linear until the temperature reaches $332.2K$, after which there is a considerable drop in p due to a rearrangement of the grains within the packing. After that, p continues to decrease until it reaches the minimum value of $0.464[\frac{kg_f}{cm^2}]$, at a temperature of $300.6K$.

Figure 18: Hydrostatic stress, p , vs temperature. As the temperature rises, p exhibits largely monotonic growth, corresponding to the thermal expansion of the grains, until the maximum stress is reached. As the temperature decreases, the grains start to reduce in volume due to thermal contraction.

The deviatoric stress, s , represents shear and distortion in the material, it is mainly associated with failure and plasticity. Figure 19 shows the relationship between the deviatoric stress, s , and the temperature in the sample. At the beginning of the simulation, s starts at $0.083[\frac{kg_f}{cm^2}]$ and then increases and decreases as the temperature rises. As the temperature begins to decline, s remains almost constant until a temperature of $332.2K$ is reached, when it immediately jumps to $0.1081[\frac{kg_f}{cm^2}]$ (its maximum level), implying that a considerable distortion occurred within the packing. As the temperature decreases further, s exhibits a noisy behavior until it converges to $0.096[\frac{kg_f}{cm^2}]$ at $300.6K$.

Figure 19: Deviatoric stress vs temperature of the 100 grain simulation. The stress varies considerably as the temperature changes, implying that there are considerable distortions happening within the packing.

In both cases, the hydrostatic and deviatoric stress (Figures 18 and 19, respectively) demonstrate a dependence of the packing state on its past thermal history, meaning that the packing exhibits different behaviors when it is being heated vs. when it is being cooled. This indicates a type of hysteresis phenomenon. As mentioned in section 1, grains expand when heated and contract when cooled in a linear fashion in the small deformation regime. However, the response of the packing is plastic (nonlinear), mainly due to the internal rearrangements within. This largely irreversible change in the internal configuration of the grains inside of the packaging can be understood through the fabric tensor since it provides a statistical measure of the spatial arrangement of the grains and of the contacts inside of a material and helps to link the microstructure of a granular material to its macroscopic behavior. Thus, through the principal directions of the fabric tensor, depicted in Figure 20, it is possible to observe a difference in the initial (red vectors) and final (blue vectors) configuration of the packing after the heating and cooling process. The difference is significant when considering the first and third principal directions, with a change of 15.96° and 15.69° , respectively, between the initial and final positions after having undergone the heating-cooling process.

Figure 20: Fabric tensor principal directions at the beginning (red arrows) and end (blue arrows) of the heating-cooling process.

8.4 Optimization outcomes

Finally, the results of having leveraged the capabilities of Intel’s MKL and NVIDIA’s CUDA are shown. The simulation times are represented in Figure 21, initially requiring about 37.6 hours to finish without the optimizations. With the use of the MKL, the simulation time drops to 29 hours (a 22.87% improvement). By implementing both MKL and CUDA, the simulation time drops to 5.3 hours (an 85.90% improvement overall), indicating a definite advantage in using the GPUs for computing the FEM matrix operations.

Figure 21: Simulation time comparison (in hours) when using only the Eigen library, the MKL-enhanced Eigen library, and when using both the MKL-enhanced Eigen + the CUDA optimization are implemented in the code. Eigen takes almost 40 hours to run the simulation, while the best results were given by the MKL + CUDA combination, where the simulation time drops to 5.3 hours.

9 Further improvements

- For our multi-body heat conduction scheme, at any time step, t , we assumed that a grain was at an average temperature in order to compute the heat flow at the contact point between two grains. A more consistent process implies solving a point-to-element contact model for the heat flow computation at the contact point, which unfortunately, would result in an unaffordable computational cost.
- For integrating $\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t)$, we have chosen a forward Euler finite differences scheme, however, other methods such as the Crank-Nicholson method with second-order accuracy could be considered in the future.
- The meshing process has been chosen to capture the grain volume with a reasonable level of fidelity while also maintaining an affordable computational cost. Nevertheless, higher-order elements or denser meshing algorithms could be considered for gaining accuracy in the computation of the FEM equations [42].
- In our approach, the implementation of CUDA for solving the FEM equations had an enormous impact on the computation time. Despite this, our implementation was limited to a single GPU. In future investigations, the sample domain could be segmented in order to dis-

tribute the FEM computations onto different GPUs, which could considerably increase the scalability of this approach.

10 Conclusions

The present investigation introduced a generalized 3DLS-DEM + FEM scheme that allows, for the first time, the efficient simulation of heat conduction and thermal volumetric expansion in arbitrarily shaped granular media. This adopted generalized approach is capable of preserving the grain mass and morphology with high fidelity, thus allowing for a deep understanding of the role played by different grain-scale phenomena on the macroscopic mechanical behavior of a given granular material. This new 3DLS-DEM + FEM scheme was evaluated through two computational tests. The first simulation (benchmark) was intended to fine-tune the model parameters, to match the Cauchy stress tensor geometry, test the physics, and exhibit the capabilities of our scheme. The benchmark test in question allowed to assess how fast the average packing temperature converged to the prescribed temperature. Additionally, given that the packing matches the Cauchy stress tensor geometry (a cube), it was possible to analyze the evolution of the Cauchy stress tensor coordinates over time and their relationship with the temperature, which gives a deep understanding of how the packing stress responds to the grain volumetric expansion induced by thermal changes.

On the other hand, the second test is a use-case scenario that was inspired by a real study related to the potential effects of the thermal impact of exothermic wastes on excavation in clayey host rocks at great depth. Using a fixed convex hull system, it was possible to replicate the geometry and the heating-cooling process for an Opalinus clay sample under drained conditions for our use-case scenario. However, since the numerical solution of the thermal problem is achieved by the Finite Element Method (FEM), where large matrix operations are involved, our scheme encountered an important bottleneck. The C++ standard linear algebra library Eigen by itself, turned very inefficient, for which, the matrix operations were optimized with the use of Intel's Math Kernel Library (MKL) and the NVIDIA's Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA), resulting in a drastic reduction in the simulation time. From the results obtained in the use-case scenario test, it was possible to observe that when the heating-cooling process was applied, the grains expanded and contracted within the packing, which causes the contact points among grains

vary over time. As a consequence of the grains expansion-contraction the hydrostatic, p , and deviatoric, s , stresses exhibit a hysteretic behavior, showing a direct implication of the thermal phenomenon on the mechanical response of the packing, as well as on its internal configuration (fabric tensor). The hysteresis, thermal stress, and fabric tensor, lead to conclude that the packing as a whole behaves plastically, even though each individual grain is subjected only to linear-elastic changes.

11 CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sebastián A. Pazmiño: Writing, Methodology, Conceptualization, Coding, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis.

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13 Appendix

13.1 Element’s volume

$$V^{(e)} = \frac{1}{6} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & x_i^{(e)} & y_i^{(e)} & z_i^{(e)} \\ 1 & x_j^{(e)} & y_j^{(e)} & z_j^{(e)} \\ 1 & x_k^{(e)} & y_k^{(e)} & z_k^{(e)} \\ 1 & x_l^{(e)} & y_l^{(e)} & z_l^{(e)} \end{vmatrix}$$

13.2 Element’s Jacobian

$$\mathbf{J}^{(e)} = \begin{pmatrix} (x_2 - x_1) & (y_2 - y_1) & (z_2 - z_1) \\ (x_3 - x_1) & (y_3 - y_1) & (z_3 - z_1) \\ (x_4 - x_1) & (y_4 - y_1) & (z_4 - z_1) \end{pmatrix}$$

13.3 Shape functions coefficients

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_i^{(e)} = (-1)^{(j+k+l+1)} \begin{vmatrix} x_j^{(e)} & y_j^{(e)} & z_j^{(e)} \\ x_k^{(e)} & y_k^{(e)} & z_k^{(e)} \\ x_l^{(e)} & y_l^{(e)} & z_l^{(e)} \end{vmatrix} \\ c_i^{(e)} = (-1)^{(j+k+l)} \begin{vmatrix} x_j^{(e)} & 1 & z_j^{(e)} \\ x_k^{(e)} & 1 & z_k^{(e)} \\ x_l^{(e)} & 1 & z_l^{(e)} \end{vmatrix} \end{array} \right. \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} b_i^{(e)} = (-1)^{(j+k+l)} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & y_j^{(e)} & z_j^{(e)} \\ 1 & y_k^{(e)} & z_k^{(e)} \\ 1 & y_l^{(e)} & z_l^{(e)} \end{vmatrix} \\ d_i^{(e)} = (-1)^{(j+k+l)} \begin{vmatrix} x_j^{(e)} & y_j^{(e)} & 1 \\ x_k^{(e)} & y_k^{(e)} & 1 \\ x_l^{(e)} & y_l^{(e)} & 1 \end{vmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

13.4 Stiffness matrix coefficients

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 K_{11} = b_1^{(e)2} + c_1^{(e)2} + d_1^{(e)2} \\
 K_{12} = b_1^{(e)}b_2^{(e)} + c_1^{(e)}c_2^{(e)} + d_1^{(e)}d_2^{(e)} \\
 K_{13} = b_1^{(e)}b_3^{(e)} + c_1^{(e)}c_3^{(e)} + d_1^{(e)}d_3^{(e)} \\
 K_{14} = b_1^{(e)}b_4^{(e)} + c_1^{(e)}c_4^{(e)} + d_1^{(e)}d_4^{(e)} \\
 K_{21} = K_{12} \\
 K_{22} = b_2^{(e)2} + c_2^{(e)2} + d_2^{(e)2} \\
 K_{23} = b_2^{(e)}b_3^{(e)} + c_2^{(e)}c_3^{(e)} + d_2^{(e)}d_3^{(e)} \\
 K_{24} = b_2^{(e)}b_4^{(e)} + c_2^{(e)}c_4^{(e)} + d_2^{(e)}d_4^{(e)} \\
 K_{31} = K_{13} \\
 K_{32} = K_{23} = \\
 K_{33} = b_3^{(e)2} + c_3^{(e)2} + d_3^{(e)2} \\
 K_{34} = b_3^{(e)}b_4^{(e)} + c_3^{(e)}c_4^{(e)} + d_3^{(e)}d_4^{(e)} \\
 K_{41} = K_{14} \\
 K_{42} = K_{24} \\
 K_{43} = K_{34} \\
 K_{44} = b_4^{(e)2} + c_4^{(e)2} + d_4^{(e)2}
 \end{array} \right.$$

13.5 Neumann's boundary conditions vector (heat flow)

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{f}_{123}^{(e)} = -\bar{q} \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{6} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{f}_{134}^{(e)} = -\bar{q} \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{6} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{f}_{1234}^{(e)} = -Q^e V^e \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{f}_{124}^{(e)} = -\bar{q} \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{6} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{f}_{234}^{(e)} = -\bar{q} \frac{|\mathbf{J}^{(e)}|}{6} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \text{Element's heat source term} \end{array}$$